

Science & Technology
Facilities Council

Environmental Data Archival: Practices and Benefits

Graham Parton
graham.parton@stfc.ac.uk

With many thanks to Dr Sarah Callaghan

Transmission, presentation and archiving of meteorological data

**British Atmospheric
Data Centre**

NATIONAL CENTRE FOR ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

**Centre for Environmental
Data Archival**
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

**National Centre for
Earth Observation**

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Quick into about CEDA

The screenshot shows the website for the Centre for Environmental Data Archival. At the top, there is a header with the Science and Technology Facilities Council logo and the text 'Centre for Environmental Data Archival'. Below this is a navigation menu with links for 'About CEDA', 'Data Centres', 'Services', 'Projects', 'For Academics', 'For Business', 'Help', and 'Contact Us'. The main content area is titled 'Data Centres' and contains a paragraph stating that the Centre is responsible for running several data centres. These are listed in three columns: 1. British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC), described as NERC's designated data centre for the UK atmospheric science community. 2. NERC Earth Observation Data Centre (NEODC), described as NERC's designated data centre for Earth Observation data. 3. IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC), described as providing climate, socio-economic and environmental data from the past and future scenarios. The footer of the screenshot shows logos for the British Atmospheric Data Centre, the Centre for Environmental Data Archival, and the National Centre for Earth Observation.

Centre for Environmental Data Archival
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

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Data Centres

The Centre for Environmental Data Archival is responsible for the running of the following data centres:

British Atmospheric Data Centre
NATIONAL CENTRE FOR ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

The British Atmospheric Data Centre

The British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC), NERC's designated data centre for the UK atmospheric science community, covering climate, composition, observations and NWP data.

NEODC

NERC Earth Observation Data Centre

The NEODC is NERC's designated data centre for Earth Observation data and is part of NERC's National Centre for Earth Observation.

ipcc

IPCC Data Distribution Centre

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) DDC provides climate, socio-economic and environmental data, both from the past and also in scenarios projected into the future. Technical guidelines on the selection and use of different types of data and scenarios in research and assessment are also provided.

The UK Solar System Data Centre

The UK Solar System Data Centre, co-funded by STFC and NERC, curates and provides access to archives of data from the upper atmosphere, ionosphere and Earth's solar environment.

CEDA and NERC

The UK's Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) funds six data centres which between them have responsibility for the long-term management of NERC's environmental data holdings.

We deal with a variety of environmental measurements, along with the results of model simulations in:

- Atmospheric science
- Earth sciences
- Earth observation
- Marine Science
- Polar Science
- Terrestrial & freshwater science, Hydrology and Bioinformatics

Science & Technology
Facilities Council

But...

Why archive data anyway?

**British Atmospheric
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NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

The “Scientific” Method

The “Scientific” Method

Scientific method built on:

reproducibility and
transparency of method and results

Allows peers to critique

- method – reasoned approach to collect data
- results - analysed and synthesised= plots
- conclusions – results correctly interpreted

Published in peer reviewed literature...

Thanks to Nik Papageorgiou : <http://upmic.wordpress.com/>

Traditionally: Everything in Journals.. Including data

Suber cells and mimosa leaves. Robert Hooke, Micrographia, 1665

[Observations of Stars in the Spiral Nebula. H. 1622.

The spiral form of this nebula is very distinctly seen in the Pulkova refractor. Unfortunately in the month of March, the best season for the observation of this object, the sky was constantly cloudy; so that I could only get three nights' observations in the months of April and May, when the twilight did not cease for the whole night. It must be attributed to this unfavourable circumstance that the following list of determinations is not so complete as it probably would have been without the twilight. The observations have been made alternately with powers of 138 and 207.

Observations.

Date.	Object.	Magnitude.	Ang. Pos.	No. of measures.	Distance.	No. of measura.
1851, April 7.	N n	14° 55'	5	867.1	4
	N a	a = (11)	229 24	3	88.0	3
	N b	b = (11.12)	109 12	3	242.6	3
April 28.	a b	93 42	3	298.6	4
	N a	228 35	4	300.8	
	N b	188 54	4		
	n a	283 42	3		
	n b	153 30	3		
	a d	d = (12.13)	323 51	3		
	N d	277 27	3		
	a e	e = (13)	112 13	3		
	N e	161 56	3		
	N f	f = (12.13)	309 18	3		
	n f	237 31	3		
	a f	335 23	3		
May 3.	a g	g = (12.13)	215 17	3		115.5
	a h	h = (12.13)	193 29	3		
	g h	87 5	3		
	N h	h = (12.14)	51 47	3		
	w h	173 29	4		
	h k	317 23	3		
	h l	l = (11.12)	27 20	4		
	w l	83 17	4	335.2	4
	a e	112 56	4		
	N e	161 39	3		
	a m	m = (12.13)	172 43	5		
		N m	190 44	4	
b m		238 50	4		
N a		229 12	4	87.0	3
N n		14 47	4	264.2	3

The Scientific Papers of William Parsons, Third Earl of Rosse 1800-1867

New paradigm: NOT Everything in Journals

...but datasets are now very large volume:

CERN ~15 petabytes data produced annually

DNA ~ 1 exabyte of genome data by 2014

Climate change -

CMIP5: Fifth Coupled Model Intercomparison Project

Produced data underpinning next IPCC report

The World in Global Climate Models

FAR:1990
SAR:1995
TAR:2001
AR4:2007
AR5:2013

CMIP5 numbers!

Simulations:

- ~90,000 years
 - ~60 experiments
 - ~20 modelling centres (from around the world) using
 - ~30 major(*) model configurations
 - ~2 million output “atomic” datasets
 - ~10's of petabytes of output
 - ~2 petabytes of CMIP5 requested output
 - ~1 petabyte of CMIP5 “replicated” output
- Which are replicated at a number of sites (including ours)

Of the replicants:

- ~ 220 TB decadal
- ~ 540 TB long term
- ~ 220 TB atmosphere-only

- ~80 TB of 3hourly data
- ~215 TB of ocean 3d monthly data
- ~250 TB for the cloud feedbacks
- ~10 TB of land-biochemistry (from the long term experiments alone)

So, SCALE of data means its no longer possible to publish data anymore...

So what is under threat?

Reproducibility and **transparency**

How do we answer this? Do we even care?

What are our options?

Are synthesis/plots sufficient?

Just carry on with small scale datasets alone?

Just reproduce the data?....

Or just get on and archive the stuff?

Creating a dataset is hard work!

DATA: BY THE NUMBERS

www.phdcomics.com

"Piled Higher and Deeper" by Jorge Cham
www.phdcomics.com

Why should I bother putting my data into a repository?

THE FOUR STAGES OF DATA LOSS

DEALING WITH ACCIDENTAL DELETION OF MONTHS OF
HARD-EARNED DATA

"Piled Higher and Deeper" by Jorge Cham
www.phdcomics.com

It's ok, I'll just do regular backups

	a	e	i	o/u
y	⊠	⊗	⊙	⊚
w	⊡	⊞	⊜	⊛
r	⊢	⊟	⊝	⊣
m	⊣	⊠	⊙	⊚
n	⊤	⊞	⊙	⊚
p	⊢	⊞	⊙	⊚
t	⊢	⊞	⊙	⊚
d	⊢	⊞	⊙	⊚
k	⊢	⊞	⊙	⊚
q	⊢	⊞	⊙	⊚
s	⊢	⊞	⊙	⊚
z	⊢	⊞	⊙	⊚

non-placés: L8 ⊠ (ya₂?); e1 ⊙ (q₁?); 35 ⊙ (ma₂?); 36 ⊙ (ko₂?)

L37 ⊙ (qa₂?); 43 ⊠ (wa₂?); 65 ⊙ (ki₂?); 90 ⊙ (ka₂?).

filum of Linear A'

Phaistos Disk, 1700BC

These documents have been preserved for thousands of years!
But they've both been translated many times, with different meanings each time.

Data Preservation is not enough, we need Active Curation to preserve Information

1. It costs time, effort and money to create it
2. Not all data are reproducible!
3. There is added benefit too in data re-use

CORRAL Project :

UK Colonial Registers and Royal Navy
Logbooks

Initial costs of collecting the data in C19th
300 logbooks producing some
40,000 images

Useful for historical researchers & climate
scientists

DDS Discovery Service
sharing NERC data

Home About the DDS Search for data Your comments About NERC science Contact us

Results RSS Atom

Your search returned **13** results. Showing **all results** (help). You may like related search terms (show)

You are searching for...
documents containing rain in **62.00N 49.00S 4.00E -10.00W** Only returning records with an online resource.
13 results returned in **4.07** seconds.

Change the number of results per page.

Dataset description	Resource type	Online resource
1. Met Office - MIDAS Land Surface Stations data (1853-current) Land surface observations data from the Met Office station network and other world wide stations as stored in the Met Office MIDAS database. Data are available for the period 1853 to present. The dataset comprises daily and hourly weather measurement... [more]	series	yes
2. Met Office - Land Surface Stations data (1900-2000) Historic land surface observations data from the Met Office station network. Data are available for the period 1900 to 1999 for daily measurements. Hourly observations are for now available back to January 1985. The dataset comprises daily and hou... [more]	series	yes
3. Bolton Experiment Microwave attenuation and rain gauge data from the Bolton experiment	series	yes
4. Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR) Data from observations made using Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR).The Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) facility at Chilbolton Observatory, Hampshire (51.1445N, 1.4270W) is the home of many observatio... [more]	series	yes
5. Time series of water levels and chemical parameters in Blind Beck and Low Hall stream, Eden Time series data (15 minute resolution) was collected using WISER station on Blind Beck (NY 753131) and on a tributary of Blind Beck (Low Hall stream NY 753130), to investigate the different flow pathways suggested by the different chemical si... [more]	series	yes
6. Monitoring of the Blind Beck subcatchment of the River Eden,	series	yes

bring Earth from space

a) to discover and gain products. The metadata are and are provided to the

dataset yes records of interest by identify which records to be full details of each

NERC Data Catalogue Service
data-search.nerc.ac.uk

Bonus material: Data Services

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled "ISIC Visualisation - International Space Innovation Centre, Harwell Oxford". The main content area features the ISIC logo and a world map. On the left side, there is a "Datasets" panel with a tree view containing folders for "Earth Observation Data", "Model Data", "Mars Data", "Outline Map", and "Temporary Map Services". Below this is a "Layers" panel with a single layer "Outline Map" which is checked. At the bottom of the interface, there is a footer for the "Centre for Environmental Data Archival" with its logo and contact information: "SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL" and "NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL". A phone number "-177.37773, 50.57232" is also visible in the bottom right corner of the application window.

The research data lifecycle

Researchers are used to creating, processing and analysing data.

Data repositories generally have the job of preserving and giving access to data.

Third parties, or even the original researchers will reuse the data.

See <http://data-archive.ac.uk/create-manage/life-cycle> for more detail

What is a Dataset?

DataCite's definition

(http://www.datacite.org/sites/default/files/Business_Models_Principles_v1.0.pdf):

Dataset: "Recorded information, regardless of the form or medium on which it may be recorded including writings, films, sound recordings, pictorial reproductions, drawings, designs, or other graphic representations, procedural manuals, forms, diagrams, work flow, charts, equipment descriptions, data files, data processing or computer programs (software), statistical records, and other research data." (from the U.S. National Institutes of Health (NIH) Grants Policy Statement via DataCite's Best Practice Guide for Data Citation).

A dataset is something that is:

- The result of a **defined process**
- **Scientifically meaningful**
- **Well-defined** (i.e. clear definition of what is in the dataset and what isn't)

Reasons for citing and publishing data

- **Pressure** from (UK) **government** to make data from publicly funded research available for free.
 - **Scientists** want **attribution** and **credit** for their work
 - **Public** want to know what the scientists are doing
 - Good for the **economy** if new industries can be built on scientific data/research
- Research **fundors** want reassurance that they're getting **value for money**
 - Relies on peer-review of science publications (well established) and data (starting to be done!)
- Allows the wider **research community** and **industry** to **find and use** datasets, and understand the **quality** of the data
- Extra **incentive** for scientists to submit their data to data centres in appropriate formats and with full metadata

<http://www.evidencebased-management.com/blog/2011/11/04/new-evidence-on-big-bonuses/>

Knowledge is power!

Data may mean the difference between getting a grant and not.

There is (currently) no universally accepted mechanism for data creators to obtain academic credit for their dataset creation efforts.

Creators (understandably) prefer to hold the data until they have extracted all the possible publication value they can.

This behaviour comes at a cost for the wider scientific community.

But if we publish the data, precedence is established and credit is given!

How to publish data

By David Fletcher

<http://www.cloudtweaks.com/2011/05/the-lighter-side-of-the-cloud-data-transfer/>

- Stick it up on a webpage somewhere
 - Issues with stability, persistence, discoverability...
 - Maintenance of the website
- Put it in the cloud
 - Issues with stability, persistence, discoverability...
- Attach it to a journal paper and store it as supplementary materials
 - Journals not too keen on archiving lots of supplementary data, especially if it's large volume.
- Put it in a disciplinary/institutional repository
- Write a data article about it and publish it in a data journal

“Publishing” versus “p_uublishing” and “Open” versus “Closed”

Distinction between:

Publishing = publishing after some formal process which adds value for the consumer:

- e.g. PloS ONE type review, or
- EGU journal type public review, or
- More traditional peer review.

and

- provides commitment to persistence

And **p_uublishing**/serving = making available for consumption (e.g. on the web)

What do we need to support publishing data?

The **scientific quality** of a dataset has to be evaluated by **peer-review** by scientists with domain knowledge. This peer-review process has already been set up by academic publishers, so it makes sense to collaborate with them for peer-review publishing of data.

Can cite using URLs, but we've realised that people don't trust URLs
We're loading DOIs with more meaning than them simply being a persistent identifier – using them to signify **completeness** and **technical quality** of the dataset.

The **day job** – take in data and metadata supplied by scientists (often on a on-going basis). Make sure that there is adequate metadata and that the data files are appropriate format. Make it available to other interested parties.

- We already have a working method for linking between publications which is:
 - commonly used
 - understood by the research community
 - used to create metrics to show how much of an impact something has (citation counts)
 - applied to digital objects (digital versions of journal articles)
- We can extend citation to other things like:
 - data
 - code
 - multimedia

And the best bit is, researchers don't need to learn a new method of linking – they cite like they normally would!

<http://www.naa.gov.au/records-management/capability-development/keep-the-knowledge/index.aspx>

How we (formally) cite data

We use digital object identifiers (DOIs) as part of our dataset citation because:

- They are actionable, interoperable, persistent links for (digital) objects
- Scientists are already used to citing papers using DOIs (and they trust them)
- Academic journal publishers (e.g. Nature) are starting to require datasets be cited in a stable way, i.e. using DOIs.
- The British Library and DataCite approached us to pilot citing data using DOIs – and we've developed a good working relationship

The screenshot shows the DataCite Metadata Search interface. The search bar contains the query 'prefix: 10.5285'. The results page shows 44 documents found in 117ms. The first few results are:

- GBS 20 7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site [version 1.0] #1
- United Kingdom Butterfly Monitoring Scheme: Collated Indices 2011 #2
- CTD profiles (depth, pressure, temperature, salinity, potential temperature, density, fluorescence, transmittance, downwelling PAR, dissolved oxygen concentration) binned to 0.5 m and 0.25 m at sites L4 and E1 in the Western English Channel between January 2002 and December 2011 #3
- ITE Land Classification of Great Britain 1990 #4
- ITE Land Classification of Great Britain 1998 #5
- ITE Land Classification of Great Britain 2007 #6
- Concentrations of polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) in sparrowhawk (Accipiter nisus) eggs in the UK #7
- Mars Analysis Correction Data Assimilation (MACDA): MGS/ITES v1.0 [version 1.0] #8
- Land Cover Map 2007 (1km percentage Target Class, GB) #9
- Land Cover Map 2007 (Vector, GB) #10

What sort of data can we/will we assign a DOI to?

Dataset has to be:

- Stable (i.e. not going to be modified)
- Complete (i.e. not going to be updated)
- Permanent – by assigning a DOI we’re committing to make the dataset available for posterity
- Good quality – by assigning a DOI we’re giving it our data centre stamp of approval, saying that it’s complete and all the metadata is available

When a dataset is cited that means:

- There will be bitwise fixity
- With no additions or deletions of files
- No changes to the directory structure in the dataset “bundle”

A DOI should point to a *html representation* of some *record* which describes a *data object* – i.e. a landing page.

Upgrades to versions of data formats will result in new editions of datasets.

Viewing GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site

badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

BADC - Trac METAFOR | Home Google Mail BBC NEWS | News Fr... Sorcha ni gCeallagh... Other bookmarks

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Search for in All

GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site

General Info

Title: GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site
Type: Activity
Sub-Type: Deployment
Publication State: Citable
URI: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

Summary

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset is a series of radio attenuation measurements made at three sites in the UK: Chilbolton and Sparsholt, both in southern UK, and Dundee in Scotland. The aim of the experiment was to make long term measurements of the signal strength received from a 20.7GHz beacon on the US Department of Defense satellite UFO-9 at multiple sites, in order to determine whether the use of site diversity as a fade mitigation technique would be effective. The dataset spans a period of 3 years, from August 2003 to August 2006 with signal attenuation sampled once per second.

Please cite this dataset as:
 Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras], GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site, [Internet]. British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2003-2005, 1st April 2011, doi:10.5285/639a3714-bc74-46a6-9026-64931f355e07

This dataset is cited in:
 S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, J.L.Agnew, C. J. Walden, C.L.Wrench , S. Ventouras "The GBS dataset: measurements of satellite site diversity at 20.7 GHz in the UK", Geoscience Data Journal, 17 March 2013, DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

Author

Name	email
Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras]	

Online References

Relation	Title
Apply for access	Apply for access to GBS data from Chilbolton
Download	Data directory for GBS data from Chilbolton
Documentation	DOI for dataset: 10.5285/639a3714-bc74-46a6-9026-64931f355e07
Documentation	Data article in Geoscience Data Journal doi:10.1002/gdj3.2

Associated Data

Type	Title
Data Production Tool	Chilbolton: GBS receiver
Activity	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR)
Observation Station	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR), UK

Dataset catalogue page (and DOI landing page)

Dataset citation

Clickable link to Dataset in the archive

STFC Data home | Science x
https://data.isis.stfc.ac.uk/doi/INVESTIGATION/24079886/

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search Go

STFC Programmatic Review 2012-13

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ISIS Data

RB920411.

Investigation title: Responsive polymer brushes grafted from gold nanoparticles: interaction with surfactant.

Creator: Titmuss,S
Creator: Jia,H

DOI: 10.5286/ISIS.E.24079886

Date of Experiment: Sat May 01 08:45:00 BST 2010

Publisher: STFC ISIS Facility

Data format: RAW/Nexus
Select the data format above to find out more about it.

Data Citation
The recommended format for citing this dataset in a research publication is as:
[author], [date], [title], [publisher], [doi]

For Example:
Titmuss,S. et al; (2010): 920411, STFC ISIS Facility, doi:10.5286/ISIS.E.24079886

Abstract
We will use SANS to characterize dispersions of gold nanoparticles functionalized with poly(dimethyl aminoethyl methacrylate) brushes grafted from 25 nm gold nanoparticle interfaces by surface-initiated ATRP. We will characterize the response of the polymer layers to pH and at at low pH, where the polymer is cationically charged, to electrolyte concentration. Our main focus however will be to determine the nature of the surfactant aggregates formed in the brushes at concentrations of surfactant that lead to peaks in the surface tension of the dispersions at pH=3 and 10 and also lead to the formation of multilayer structures in equivalent brushes formed at planar interfaces. We will measure under particle-matching contrast, for dispersions bearing hydrogenous pDMAMEA and particle-matching DMAEMA with particle-matching SDS and hydrogenous SDS respectively.

DOWNLOAD
download the dataset

Data collected on the SANS2D instrument at the ISIS facility

Contact us Cookies/Privacy Terms & conditions Cymraeg FOI Copyright Glossary Sitemap Accessibility

RESEARCH COUNCILS UK

Centre for
Observation
RESEARCH COUNCIL

Dataset citation

What else can be on the end of a DataCite DOI? A project report

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the National Research Council Canada website. The browser's address bar shows the URL: `nparc.cisti-icist.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/npsi/ctrl?action=shwart&index=an&req=20337846&lang=en`. The page header includes the National Research Council Canada logo and the text "Canada". The main navigation bar contains links for "Français", "Home", "Contact Us", "Help", "Search", and "canada.gc.ca". The breadcrumb trail reads "NRC Home > Library and Publications > NRC Publications Archive".

The page title is "NRC Publications Archive". A yellow box contains the text "View deposited version" and the DOI: `http://dx.doi.org/10.4224/20337846`. The main content area features the title "Assessment of the Butterfly Door as a Means of Egress".

Author(s): Proulx, G.; Higgins, D.
Affiliation: NRC Institute for Research in Construction; National Research Council Canada
Language: English
Type: Report
Series: Internal Report, Institute for Research in Construction, National Research Council Canada
Date: 1997
Description: 44 p.
Report #: IRC-IR-748
Identifier #: 7826
NPARC #: 20337846
Keywords: Human behaviour
Abstract: This research project is a joint study between fire safety researchers at the Institute for Research in Construction of the National Research Council of Canada (NRC) and the Société de transport de la communauté urbaine de Montréal (STCUM). The objective of this project was to collect information on the passengers' use of the Butterfly Door for evacuation. To obtain a complete spectrum of information, it was decided to study the daily use of the Butterfly Door, its use with a large crowd of people and its use during two evacuation drills.

At the bottom of the page, there are social media sharing options for "Bookmark and Share", "Tweet", "+1", and "Like". There are also links for "Export | Get Link" and "Report a Correction".

What else can be on the end of a DataCite DOI? Educational exhibits

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the EPOS™ (Electronic Presentation Online System) website. The URL in the address bar is posterng.netkey.at/esr/online_viewing/index.php?module=view_postercoverpage&task=viewcoverpage&doi=10.1594/ecr2012/C-1767. The page features a red header with the EPOS™ logo and the European Society of Radiology (ESR) logo. Navigation buttons for HOME, HELP, Bookmarks, and LOGIN are visible. A search bar with the text "Go to: > choose" is present.

The main content area displays the poster information for "C-1767 Biliary tree dilation – and now what?".

Poster No.: C-1767
Poster Score: 8
Type: Educational Exhibit
Keywords: Pathology, Diagnostic procedure, Ultrasound, MR, CT, Biliary Tract / Gallbladder
Authors: J. Ferreira, A. B. Ramos, S. Magalhães, M. Certo; Porto/PT
DOI: 10.1594/ecr2012/C-1767

Rate this poster: Ⓜ☆☆☆☆☆ | Overall userrating: 0.00 stars

Learning objectives

- To present a systematic diagnostic approach when biliary tree dilation is found - To review the different causes of biliary tree dilation

[read more](#)

Background

Patients with elevation of bilirubin need to be studied. Investigation normally starts with ultrasound. Ultrasound is a non-invasive and fast technique that can confirm if dilation of biliary tree is or not present, and sometimes can establish its cause. Most of the patients will need further work-up either with Computed Tomography (CT), Magnetic Resonance Cholangiopancreatography (MRCP), endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP), and ultrasound endoscopy.

[read more](#)

Imaging findings OR Procedure details

CT is an important tool to confirm ultrasound findings, such as pancreatic carcinoma, enabling at the same time disease staging. In our Hospital, because of time consuming examination and lower availability, MRCP is used for patients with suspicious diseases from the biliary tree, such as Caroli's disease or cholangiocarcinoma. In the presence of a normal CT examination, and/or unclear MRCP findings, which can happen for example in small ampullary tumour, ERCP is usually the next imaging...

[read more](#)

Conclusion

Biliary tree dilation is a common clinical challenge. Sometimes a long diagnostic workup is needed to find the cause of the obstruction.

[read more](#)

The right sidebar contains a flowchart titled "Biliary tree dilation" and two sets of medical images (A and B) showing cross-sectional scans of the biliary system.

What else can be on the end of a DataCite DOI? Images

UC3 Merritt: Object -- ark: x

https://merritt.cdlib.org/object?group=csl_uc3_mdncune&object=ark%3A%2Fb5060%2Fd2qr4v2t

Logout | Contact UC3 | Help
Logged in as Guest

 Merritt

Collection home Change collection ▾

Object: [ark:/b5060/d2qr4v2t](https://merritt.cdlib.org/object?group=csl_uc3_mdncune&object=ark%3A%2Fb5060%2Fd2qr4v2t)
[Merritt](#) > [Collection: UCLA Modular Digital Course in Undergraduate Neuroscience Education](#) > Object: [ark:/b5060/d2qr4v2t](https://merritt.cdlib.org/object?group=csl_uc3_mdncune&object=ark%3A%2Fb5060%2Fd2qr4v2t)

Grisham, William; Jones, Heidi B.; Park, Sun Hee. **Rat spinal cord image archive** (2003)

permanent link: <http://n2t.net/ark:/b5060/d2qr4v2t>
primary identifier: [ark:/b5060/d2qr4v2t](https://merritt.cdlib.org/object?group=csl_uc3_mdncune&object=ark%3A%2Fb5060%2Fd2qr4v2t)
title: Rat spinal cord image archive
creator: Grisham, William; Jones, Heidi B.; Park, Sun Hee
date: 2003
local id: doi:10.5060/D2QR4V2T
last modified: 2013-02-01 10:57 AM UTC
created: 2013-02-01 10:43 AM UTC
total size (all versions): 233.7 MB
total versions: 2

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Object Lookup

[Go](#)

Search object author, title, date or identifier.

Current Version

Version 2: 2013-02-01 10:57 AM UTC

- 11S-RDLN-1.tif
- 11S-RDLN-2.tif
- 11S-RDLN-3A.tif
- 11S-RDLN-3B.tif

[652 more files](#)

Prior Versions

Version 1: 2013-02-01 10:43 AM UTC

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Publishing data for the scholarly record

- Scientific journal publication mainly focuses on the **analysis, interpretation and conclusions** drawn from a given dataset.
- Examining the raw data that forms the dataset is more difficult, as datasets are usually stored in digital media, in a variety of (proprietary or non-standard) formats.
- **Peer-review** is generally only applied to the methodology and final conclusions of a piece of work, and **not the underlying data** itself. But if the conclusions are to stand, the **data must be of good quality**.
- A process of **data publication**, involving peer-review of datasets would be of benefit to many sectors of the academic community.

Most scientists regarded the new streamlined peer-review process as 'quite an improvement.'

<http://libguides.luc.edu/content.php?pid=5464&sid=164619>

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More of that later... for now...

The archival process...

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What do data centres do? Data Curation Lifecycle Model

The Digital Curation Centre's Curation Lifecycle Model provides a graphical, high-level overview of the stages required for successful curation and preservation of data from initial conceptualisation or receipt through the iterative curation cycle.

<http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/curation-lifecycle-model>

Open Archive Information System (OAIS)

"**an archive**, consisting of an organization of people and systems, that has accepted the **responsibility to preserve information and make it available for a Designated Community.**"

Where

"The information being maintained is deemed to **need Long Term Preservation**, even if the OAIS itself is not permanent. Long Term is long enough to be **concerned with the impacts of changing technologies, including support for new media and data formats**, or with a changing user community".

Open Archival Information System (OAIS)

SIP = Supplier Information Product
DIP = Dataset Information Product

AIP = Archive Information Product

OAIS: Responsibilities

- Determine and continue to liaise with Designated User Community.
- Negotiate and accept data from Data Providers.
- Ensure that data, etc. are independently understandable.
- Make preserved data, etc. available.
- Ensure Data, etc. are preserved.

OAIS: Functions

- Data Management
- Ingest
- Archival Storage
- Administration
- Access
- Preservation Planning
- Common Services

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Curation Problems

stories from the coal face...

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Sometimes other people don't get it.

"Piled Higher and Deeper" by Jorge Cham
www.phdcomics.com

Archiving can sometimes produce mixed feelings

"Piled Higher and Deeper" by Jorge Cham
www.phdcomics.com

Thanks to Nik Papageorgiou :
<http://upmic.wordpress.com/>

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And some ways to over come
those problems...

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Data Preparation

- Data Management Plans - agreed with PI/Programme SC
 - Delivery schedules
 - Conditions of Use/Licensing
 - Responsibilities of data providers and CEDA
 - Project specific requirements
 - 3rd party data requirements
 - shared group workspace
- Support suppliers in data preparation
 - Formats, metadata conventions
- File naming and archive structure
- Capture supporting documentation
 - (formats, calibration information, flight logs, etc.)
- Set up ingest routes

Good data and metadata formats

- Ensures future users can open data files
 - How future proof is an Excel spread sheet?
- Permits metadata harvesting from the data
- Generic extraction/processing tools for the data
- Can guarantee un-ambiguous content

Data Preparation - File structure

Take the Bad Data Challenge.... File “sw010203”

4.31	155.3	3.92	136.1	5.15	140.2	4.23	137.1	4.75	150.2	4.71	137.9
4.35	146.5	4.52	138.0	4.83	153.7	5.40	145.8	4.63	141.0	4.90	137.3
4.31	143.3	4.58	157.0	4.94	141.7	4.65	143.1	4.63	143.0	4.88	149.5
5.42	148.5	4.92	140.4	4.04	146.7	3.92	151.5	5.02	135.3	5.06	151.6
4.65	152.3	4.31	168.8	3.79	145.3	5.92	152.9	5.02	145.8	4.77	161.6
4.79	144.1	4.60	147.5	5.33	150.1	4.81	141.0	6.02	146.9	4.38	149.0
4.42	142.5	4.58	133.4	4.35	150.5	4.96	149.8	5.56	143.4	5.08	148.5
5.19	141.6	4.40	142.4	4.10	152.6	5.02	134.0	4.94	142.9	5.27	144.4
5.38	141.5	5.88	144.8	6.00	140.1	4.75	158.3	5.08	148.1	5.46	163.5
4.27	150.8	4.69	138.8	5.71	144.0	5.21	138.8	5.00	132.4	5.06	144.4

What are these data? Guess surface winds, but on what day?

What are the units? Any convention?

How do we read the file?

Is this spatial or temporal data?... 1440 pairs of data in a file

Supported Formats

```
netcdf simple {
dimensions:
    latitude = 3 ;
    longitude = 2 ;
    time = UNLIMITED ; // (5 currently);
variables:
    double time(time) ;
        time:standard_name = "time" ;
        time:units = "minutes since 1994-01-01 00:00:00" ;
        time:long_name = "time" ;
    float latitude(latitude) ;
        latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
        latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
        latitude:point_spacing = "even" ;
        latitude:long_name = "latitude" ;
    float longitude(longitude) ;
        longitude:standard_name = "longitude" ;
        longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
        longitude:point_spacing = "even" ;
        longitude:long_name = "longitude" ;
    float temp(time, latitude, longitude) ;
        temp:standard_name = "surface temperature" ;
        temp:long_name = "Surface temperature in degrees C" ;
        temp:units = "deg_C" ;
        temp:_FillValue = 2.e+020f ;
        temp:valid_min = -80.f ;
        temp:valid_max = 60.f ;
        temp:comment = "This parameter may be erroneous." ;
```

Highly structured metadata

Standard Names

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Time for metadata?

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Future role of the library

Domain specific repositories can:

- Pick and choose what data to keep
- Ask for (and get) more detailed metadata
- Provide specific tools and services (visualisations, server-side processing,...)
- Deal with Big Data!

Libraries will need to:

- Pick up and manage/archive the long-tail data where there isn't a domain repository
- Have generalised, widely applicable systems that can cope with subjects from astronomy to zoology
- Be prepared to cope with anything!

Summary and maybe conclusions?

- Data is important, and becoming more so for a far wider range of the population
- Conclusions and knowledge are only as good as the data they're based on
- Science is supposed to be reproducible and verifiable
- It's up to us as scientists to care for the data we've got and ensure that the story of what we did to the data is transparent
 - So we can use the data again
 - And so people will trust our results
- It's not an easy job – but someone's got to do it!

The Not-So-Secret life of a PI.

Thanks!

Any questions?

graham.parton@stfc.ac.uk

<http://www.scoop.it/t/windgatherer/>

sarah.callaghan@stfc.ac.uk

@sorcha_ni

<http://citingbytes.blogspot.co.uk/>

Image credit: Borepatch <http://borepatch.blogspot.com/2010/06/its-not-what-you-dont-know-that-hurts.html>

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Extra Stuff 1

Metadata

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Metadata

It is generally agreed that we need methods to:

- define and document datasets of importance.
- augment and/or annotate data
- amalgamate, reprocess and reuse data

To do this, we need **metadata** – data about data

For example:

Longitude and latitude are metadata about the planet.

- They are artificial
- They allow us to communicate about places on a sphere
- They were principally designed by those who needed to navigate the oceans, which are lacking in visible features!

http://www.kcoyle.net/meta_purpose.html

Metadata can often act as a surrogate for the real thing, in this case the planet.

Metadata for Discovery, Documentation, Definition

Lawrence et al 2009, [doi:10.1098/rsta.2008.0237](https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2008.0237)

MOLES: Metadata Objects for Linking Environmental Sciences v3.4

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/moles/browser/branches/V3.4/MODEL/Diagrams/MOLES3.4Summary.png>

MOLES3

Observation
Collection – Logical
grouping of results,
e.g. all data for a
project

Observation –
specific set of data –
the **What** (date,
time, description of
result – the **Where**,
When, **Who**)

Process – the **How**:
Acquisition |
Computation |
Composite

Project – the **Why**

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Extra Stuff 2

Data Journals

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The traditional online journal model

1) Author prepares the paper using word processing software.

2) Author submits the paper as a PDF/Word file.

3) Reviewer reviews the PDF file against the journal's acceptance criteria.

Overlay journal model for publishing data

1) Author prepares the data paper using word processing software and the dataset using appropriate tools.

2a) Author submits the data paper to the journal.

2b) Author submits the dataset to a repository.

3) Reviewer reviews the data paper and the dataset it points to against the journals acceptance criteria.

What is a data article?

A **data article** describes a dataset, giving details of its collection, processing, software, file formats, etc., without the requirement of novel analyses or ground breaking conclusions.

- the **when, how and why** data was collected and what the data-product is.

Data journals and scientific publication of data

- The NERC data centres (and other repositories) can now cite datasets using DOIs
 - we can give academic credit to those scientists who get cited
- Publication – and scientific peer-review – is the next step
- We are working with the Royal Meteorological Society and Wiley-Blackwell to operate a new data journal, the Geoscience Data Journal
- GDJ is an online-only, Open Access journal, publishing short data papers cross-linked to – and citing – datasets that have been deposited in approved data centres and awarded DOIs.

Other data journals already exist – see a list (in no particular order) at:

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/preparde/blog/DataJournalsList>

Scientific Data

www.nature.com/scientificdata/

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Reuse
Complete, curated & standardized descriptions enable the reuse of your data

Quality
Rigorous community based peer review

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Find datasets relevant to your research

Open
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[Press Release] NPG to launch Scientific Data to help scientists publish and reuse research data
April 3, 2013

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Welcome to *Scientific Data*

Scientific Data is a new open-access, online-only publication for descriptions of scientifically valuable datasets. It introduces a new type of content called the Data Descriptor, which will combine traditional narrative content with curated, structured descriptions of research data, including detailed methods and technical analyses supporting data quality. *Scientific Data* will initially focus on the life, biomedical and environmental science communities, but will be open to content from a wide range of scientific disciplines. Publications will be complementary to both traditional research journals and data repositories, and will be designed to foster data sharing and reuse, and ultimately to accelerate scientific discovery.

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Scientific Data is a new open-access, online-only publication for descriptions of scientifically valuable datasets. It introduces a new type of content called the Data Descriptor, which will combine traditional narrative content with curated, structured descriptions of research data, including detailed methods and technical analyses supporting data quality.

The GBS dataset: measure x

onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/gdj3.2/full

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Geoscience Data Journal Open Access

The GBS dataset: measurements of satellite site diversity at 20.7 GHz in the UK

S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, J. L. Agnew, C. J. Walden, C. L. Wrench, S. Ventouras

Article first published online: 17 MAR 2013
DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

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Additional Information (Show All)

How to Cite | Author Information | Publication History | Funding Information

The research presented in this paper was funded by the UK's Ofcom as part of the Spectrum Efficiency Scheme and the support of Ofcom in providing the funding for the GBS experiment is greatly appreciated.

Abstract | **Article** | References | Cited By

Keywords: site diversity; radio propagation; fade mitigation techniques

Abstract

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset is a series of radio attenuation measurements made at three sites in the UK: Chilbolton and Sparsholt, both in southern UK, and Dundee in Scotland. The aim of the experiment was to make long term measurements of the signal strength received from a 20.7 GHz beacon on the US Department of Defense satellite UFO-9 at multiple sites, in order to determine whether the use of site diversity as a fade mitigation technique would be effective. The dataset spans a period of 3 years, from August 2003 to August 2006 with signal attenuation sampled once per second.

Dataset

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset comes as 3 separate data streams:

- Identifier: doi:10.5285/639A3714-BC74-46A6-9026-64931F355E07
Creator: Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [Callaghan, S. A., J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras].
Title: GBS 20.7 GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site
publisher: NERC British Atmospheric Data Centre
Publication year: 2009
Resource type: Metadata document
Version: 1.0
- Identifier: doi:10.5285/db8d8981-1a51-4d6e-81c0-cccd9b921390
Creator: Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [Callaghan, S. A., J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras].

Live Data Paper in Geoscience Data Journal!

Dataset citation is first thing in the paper (after abstract) and is also included in reference list (to take advantage of citation count systems)

DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

Viewing GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site

badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

BADC - Trac METAFOR | Home Google Mail BBC NEWS | News Fr... Sorcha ni gCeallagh... Other bookmarks

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Search for in All

GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site

General Info

Title: GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Chilbolton site
Type: Activity
Sub-Type: Deployment
Publication State: Citable
URI: http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/view/badc.nerc.ac.uk_ATOM_dep_11902119479621181

Summary

The GBS (Global Broadcast Service) dataset is a series of radio attenuation measurements made at three sites in the UK: Chilbolton and Sparsholt, both in southern UK, and Dundee in Scotland. The aim of the experiment was to make long term measurements of the signal strength received from a 20.7GHz beacon on the US Department of Defense satellite UFO-9 at multiple sites, in order to determine whether the use of site diversity as a fade mitigation technique would be effective. The dataset spans a period of 3 years, from August 2003 to August 2006 with signal attenuation sampled once per second.

Please cite this dataset as:
 Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras], GBS 20.7GHz slant path radio propagation measurements, Sparsholt site, [Internet]. British Atmospheric Data Centre, 2003-2005. 1st April 2014. doi:10.5285/628e2714-b714-46ac-8026-64821f355e07

This dataset is cited in:
 S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, J.L.Agnew, C. J. Walden, C.L.Wrench , S. Ventouras "The GBS dataset: measurements of satellite site diversity at 20.7 GHz in the UK", Geoscience Data Journal, 17 March 2013, DOI: 10.1002/gdj3.2

Author

Name	email
Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC), Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research, [S. A. Callaghan, J. Waight, C. J. Walden, J. Agnew and S. Ventouras]	

Online References

Relation	Title
Apply for access	Apply for to GBS data from Chilbolton
Download	Data directory for GBS data from Chilbolton
Documentation	DOI for dataset:10.5285/628e2714-b714-46ac-8026-64821f355e07
Documentation	Data article in Geoscience Data Journal doi:10.1002/gdj3.2

Associated Data

Type	Title
Data Production Tool	Chilbolton: GBS receiver
Activity	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR)
Observation Station	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric and Radio Research (CFARR), UK

Dataset catalogue page (and DOI landing page) – again!

Reference to Data Article

Clickable link to Data Article

Working with Elsevier for publication to data linking

Data journals are a special case of journal publisher/data centre interactions.

There is still the need to link to data (held in repositories) from journal papers that mention/cite that data.

We're working with Elsevier to do just that.

Elsevier have updated their Guide for Authors text

Database linking | Elsevier x

www.elsevier.com/about/content-innovation/database-linking#about-database-linking

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- 3D molecular models
- AudioSlides
- Database linking**
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- Inline supplementary material
- MATLAB figures
- Mol files and InChI keys
- Phylogenetic trees
- PubChem compounds
- Careers

Database linking

About database linking Supported data repositories

How Elsevier is connecting data and research articles on ScienceDirect

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Elsevier encourages authors to deposit raw experimental data at relevant data repositories. Instructions for authors depend on the data repository: in some cases data is extracted from the article by curators, while in other cases authors need to upload their data manually. Detailed information is available with the individual data repositories given in the listing of supported databases.

How data and articles are linked

There are several ways in which we support interlinking of articles and data:

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database abbreviation: data identifier

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- **Referencing data in your article through tagging identifiers or accession numbers:** If your article contains relevant unique identifiers or accession numbers linking to information on genes, proteins, diseases, etc. or structures deposited in public databases, and you would like your article to link to that data, please identify these entities in the following way:

database abbreviation: data identifier

For example, "PDB: 1TUP" to identify the protein with accession number "1TUP" in the Protein Data Bank (PDB). Please bear in mind that an error in a letter or number will result in a dead link in the article. Database abbreviations and further examples can be found in the listing of [supported databases](#).

- **Data DOI's:** Elsevier supports [Data DOI's](#) as persistent identifiers for scientific data. If you include a data DOI in your article, it will automatically turn into a link to your data on ScienceDirect.
- **Linked data repository banners on ScienceDirect:** Elsevier collaborates with selected data repositories to show banner links next to relevant articles on ScienceDirect. This linking system requires that the data repository maintains accurate records of associations between articles and data sets. What you need to do as an author to support this type of linking depends on the data repository; see links to more information in the [supported databases](#) section.
- **Data visualization and integration applications:** In close collaboration with selected data repositories, Elsevier has developed a number of data-integration and visualization applications that are shown next to the article on ScienceDirect, e.g. the [Protein Viewer](#) (with PDB), the [PANGAEA](#) data visualization tool, and the [Genome Viewer](#) (with NCBI). These applications build further on tagged entities or banner links to visualize data and integrate it into the online reading experience.

From: <http://www.elsevier.com/about/content-innovation/database-linking#about-database-linking>

Earth, Environmental & Oceanographic Data

Data Repository	How articles and data are linked	More information
BGS GeoScenic	Authors should specify BGS GeoScenic numbers, e.g. <i>GeoScenic: P603281</i> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BGS GeoScenic homepage
EarthChem	EarthChem banners will be shown on ScienceDirect when the repository has data for the article. Data is extracted from the literature by curators.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EarthChem homepage • Example article
Marine Geoscience Data System (MGDS)	MGDS banners will be shown on ScienceDirect when the repository has data for the article.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MGDS homepage • Submitting data • Example article
Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), including BADC, BODC, EIDC, and NGDC.	Authors should include data DOI's in their manuscript.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NERC Data Centres
PANGAEA	Data integration application on ScienceDirect opens automatically for relevant articles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PANGAEA homepage • Submitting data • PANGAEA application • Example article
System for Earth Sample Registration (SESAR), registry for International Geo Sample Numbers (IGSN)	Authors should specify IGSN numbers, e.g. <i>IGSN: HRV003M16</i> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SESAR homepage • Registering samples
Woods Hole Open Access Server (WHOAS)	WHOAS banners will be shown on ScienceDirect when the repository has data for the article.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WHOAS homepage • Example article

NERC data centres are listed in Elsevier's list of supported data repositories.

<http://www.elsevier.com/about/content-innovation/database-linking#supported-data-repositories>

Elsevier working with NGDC to link through accession numbers

The screenshot shows the British Geological Survey GeoScenic website. The header includes the BGS logo, the text 'British Geological Survey NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL', and the 'GeoScenic' title. There are links for 'Register', 'Log In', and 'Help for this page', along with a search box. The main content area is titled 'Digital Asset' and includes a breadcrumb trail: 'You are here: Categories > Best of BGS Images > Fossils > P100659 (1 of 226 in Fossils)'. Below this is a navigation bar with 'Normal view' and 'Large image view' buttons. The central image shows a collection of fossil shells. To the right of the image are buttons for 'add to my lightbox' and 'large image popup'. Below the image is a metadata table:

P number:	P100659
Old photograph number:	P100659
Caption:	Brachiopods from the Falkland Islands. Schellwienella Sulivani (large shells) australocoelia Palmata (small shells).
Photographer:	Unknown
Copyright statement:	NERC
Orientation:	Landscape

Hyperlinked GeoScenic Accession Numbers in the article main text
(e.g. “GeoScenic: P100659”) – tagged by authors
Available for all Elsevier geology journals

Thanks to Bethan Keall (Elsevier)

Elsevier's updated Guide for Authors text

Linking with data sets

The journal would like to encourage authors to link to relevant data sets underpinning their research publication which are archived in recognised data centres, such as those of the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC). The preferred way to do this is by adding the DOI of the data set into the manuscript. Elsevier will turn these DOI's into links in the online article, making it easy for readers to find data pertinent to the published article. Elsevier would also like to encourage authors to deposit the data that supports their publication in an appropriate data archive.

<http://strangefunny.com/research-cat-says/>

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a ScienceDirect article. The browser's address bar shows the URL: www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0265931X11003031. The page header includes the ScienceDirect logo and navigation links like 'Home', 'Publications', 'Search', 'My settings', 'My alerts', and 'Shopping cart'. A search bar is visible in the top right corner.

The article title is "Observations of Fukushima fallout in Great Britain" from the "Journal of Environmental Radioactivity", Volume 114, December 2012, Pages 48–53. The authors listed are N.A. Beresford^a, C.L. Barnett^a, B.J. Howard^a, D.C. Howard^a, C. Wells^a, A.N. Tyler^b, S. Bradley^b, and D. Copplestone^b. The abstract states: "Following the Fukushima accident in March 2011, grass samples were collected from 42 sites around Great Britain during April 2011. Iodine-131 was measurable in grass samples across the country with activity concentrations ranging from 10 to 55 Bq kg⁻¹ dry matter. Concentrations were similar to those reported in other European countries. Rainwater and some foodstuffs were also analysed from a limited number of sites. Of these, ¹³¹I was only detectable in sheep's milk (c. 2 Bq kg⁻¹). Caesium-134, which can be attributed to releases from the Fukushima reactors, was detectable in six of the grass samples (4–8 Bq kg⁻¹ dry matter); ¹³⁷Cs was detected in a larger number of grass samples although previous release sources (atmospheric weapons test and the 1986 Chernobyl and 1957 Windscale accidents) are likely to have contributed to this."

On the right side of the page, there is a sidebar with 'Bibliographic information' and 'Article history'. The 'Bibliographic information' section includes the journal title, volume, issue, and DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvrad.2011.12.008>. The 'Article history' section shows the article was received on 4 August 2011, revised on 7 December 2011, accepted on 9 December 2011, and available online on 27 December 2011.

At the bottom left, there is a logo for the 'British Data Centre' and a logo for the 'Wellcome Trust/DBT India Alliance' with the text 'Early Career Fellowships in Biomedical Research'.

Database linking | Elsevier | ScienceDirect.com - Journ | CEH Information Gateway | CEH Information Gateway

← → ↻ 🏠 🔒 <https://gateway.ceh.ac.uk/terraCatalog/Start.do> ☆ 🍷 🐱 ☰

CEH Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

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dataset

Observations of Fukushima Fallout in Great Britain

Following the Fukushima accident in March 2011, grass samples were collected from 42 sites around Great Britain during April 2011. Iodine-131 was measurable in grass samples across the country with activity concentrations ranging from 10 to 55 Bq per kg ...

Description | Categorisation | Access | Distribution | Quality | Metadata

Description

Title:	Observations of Fukushima Fallout in Great Britain
Abstract:	Following the Fukushima accident in March 2011, grass samples were collected from 42 sites around Great Britain during April 2011. Iodine-131 was measurable in grass samples across the country with activity concentrations ranging from 10 to 55 Bq per kg dry matter. Concentrations were similar to those reported in other European countries. Rainwater and some foodstuffs were also analysed from a limited number of sites. Of these, I-131 was only detectable in sheep's milk (c. 2 Bq/kg). Caesium-134, which can be attributed to releases from the Fukushima reactors, was detectable in six of the grass samples (4-8 Bq/kg dry matter); 137Cs was detected in a larger number of grass samples although previous release sources (atmospheric weapons test and the 1986 Chernobyl and 1957 Windscale accidents) are likely to have contributed to this. All data and information for this sampling are available from this record. The data result from collaboration between CEH and the University of Stirling.
Resource Status:	completed
Dateset Reference Date:	creation: 2011-08-03 publication: 2011-12-31
Other Citation Details:	Beresford, N. A., Barnett, C. L., Howard, B. J., Howard, D. C., Tyler, A. N., Bradley, S., Copplestone, D. (2011) Observations of Fukushima Fallout in Great Britain. NERC- Environmental Information Data Centre doi:10.5285/1a91c7d1-ec44-4858-9af2-98d80f169bbd Link: http://dx.doi.org/10.5285/1a91c7d1-ec44-4858-9af2-98d80f169bbd
Point of Contact:	Role: author Individual name: Beresford, N.A. Organisation name: Centre for Ecology & Hydrology Position: - Phone: - Facsimile: - Delivery point: CEH Lancaster City: - Administrative area: -

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Archaeological Data Service	Social Sciences	University of York
Array Express	Life Sciences	European Bioinformatics Institute
Association of Religion Data Archives	Arts and Humanities	Pennsylvania State University
Australian Antarctic Data Centre	Climatology	Australian Government; Department of Sustainability, Environment, Water, Population and Communities
Australian Data Archive	Social Sciences	Australian National University
BioMaqResBank	Life Sciences	University of Wisconsin
British Antarctic Survey	Physical Sciences	Natural Environment Research Council
British Atmospheric Data Centre	Atmospheric Science	Natural Environment Research Council
British Geological Survey	Physical Sciences	Natural Environment Research Council
British Oceanographic Data Centre	Physical Sciences	Natural Environment Research Council
CAATray	Life Sciences	National Cancer Institute
caNanoLab	Life Sciences	National Cancer Institute
CanGEM	Life Sciences	University of Helsinki
CEBS	Life Sciences	The National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences
Cell Centered Database	Neuroscience	University of California
Centre for Ecology and Hydrology	Physical Sciences	Natural Environment Research Council
Codex Sinaiticus	Arts and Humanities	The British Library/ Leipzig University Library/ St. Catherine's Monastery/ The National Library of Russia
CPLA	Life Sciences	University of Science and Technology of China
Crystallography Open Database	Physical Sciences	Vilnius University*
Disprot	Life Sciences	Indiana University School of Medicine/ Temple University
DrugBank	Life Sciences	University of Alberta*
Dryad	Life Sciences	National Evolutionary Synthesis Center
EcoGene	Life Sciences	University of Miami
eCrystals	Crystallography	University of Southampton
Emage	Life Sciences	Medical Research Council
EMDB	Life Sciences	European Bioinformatics Institute
Esther	Life Sciences	French National Institute for Agricultural Research*
Eurostat	Social Sciences	European Union
Finnish Social Science Data Archive	Social Sciences	University of Tampere
Gene Expression Omnibus	Genetics	National Center for Biotechnology Information

DCI list of repositories

Greengenes	Life Sciences	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory
GWAS Central	Life Sciences	University of Leicester*
Infevers	Life Sciences	Institute of Human Genetics*
Inter University Consortium for Political and Social Research	Social Sciences	University of Michigan
IQSS	Social Sciences	Harvard University
Michigan Corpus of Academic Spoken English	Arts and Humanities	University of Michigan
Microkit	Life Sciences	University of Science and Technology of China
miRBase	Life Sciences	University of Manchester
Mouse Phenome Database	Life Sciences	The Jackson Laboratory
National Archives	Social Sciences	U.S. National Archives and Records Administration
National Snow and Ice Data Centre	Environmental Science	University of Colorado, Boulder
NERC Earth Observation Data Centre	Physical Sciences	Natural Environment Research Council
nmrshiftdb2	Chemistry	Johannes Gutenberg University*
NOAA Paleoclimatology	Physical Sciences	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
Nucleic Acid Database	Life Sciences	Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey
Oak Ridge National Laboratory Distributed Active Archive Center	Multi-discipline	U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration
Odum Institute	Social Sciences	Odum Institute, University of North Carolina
Office for National Statistics	Social Sciences	UK Statistics Authority
Old Bailey Proceedings Online	Arts and Humanities	Humanities Research Institute
Pangaea	Earth Sciences	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research/ Center for Marine Environmental Sciences, University of Bremen
PHI-base	Life Sciences	Rothamsted Research
Protein Data Bank	Life Sciences	Research Collaboratory for Structural Bioinformatics
Pseudobase	Life Sciences	Institute of Theoretical Biology/ Leiden Institute of Chemistry, Leiden University
QTL Archive	Life Sciences	The Jackson Laboratory
Reading Experience Database	Arts and Humanities	The Open University
Refold	Life Sciences	Monash University*
Roper Center	Social Sciences	Roper Center, University of Connecticut
Sloan Digital Sky Survey	Astronomy	Astrophysical Research Consortium
South African Data Archive	Social Sciences	National Research Foundation
Stanford Microarray Database	Genetics	Stanford School of Medicine

http://wokinfo.com/products_tools/multidisciplinary/dci/repositories/

What we've done and how we've done it

Data paper has been published in a data journal, linked via DOI to underlying dataset. Formal citations of datasets (also using DOIs) done in standard academic articles.

Can cite using URLs, but we've realised that people don't trust URLs. We're loading DOIs with more meaning than them simply being a persistent identifier – using them to signify completeness and technical quality of the dataset. We're also looking at citation counts as metric for dataset impact.

The day job – take in data and metadata supplied by scientists (often on a on-going basis). Make sure that there is adequate metadata and that the data files are appropriate format. Make it available to other interested parties.

Conclusions

- The NERC data centres now have the ability to mint DOIs and assign them to datasets in their archives. We have also produced:
 - guidelines for the data centre on what is an appropriate dataset to cite
 - guidelines for data providers about data citation and the sort of datasets we will cite
 - text in the NERC grants handbook telling grant applicants about data citation
- Other data centres/repositories/libraries are also minting DOIs for their data
- We're progressing well with data publication through our partnership with Wiley-Blackwell, and discussions with Elsevier and Thompson-Reuters. NERC held datasets have been published in data journals and cited in papers.
- Still plenty of work to do! Not just mechanical processes (e.g. workflows, guidelines) but also changing the culture so that citing and publishing data is the norm.

<http://www.keepcalm-o-matic.co.uk/default.aspx#createposter>

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Extra Stuff 3

Workflows

**British Atmospheric
Data Centre**

NATIONAL CENTRE FOR ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCE
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

**Centre for Environmental
Data Archival**

SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

**National Centre for
Earth Observation**

NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Data repository workflows

- Workflows are very varied! No one-size fits all method
- Can have multiple workflows in the same data centre, depending on interactions with external sources (“Engaged submitter”/ “Data dumper” / “Third party requester”)

